

Studies in Acenaphthenone. Part III, On the Reactivity of its 'CH₂' Group.

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Recently some patents have been taken for the production of vat dyes by the condensation of acenaphthenone with 2:3-diketodihydrothionaphthene (D.R.P. 226244) and its derivatives (D.R.P. 218992) and with derivatives of isatin or naphthisatin (D.R.P. 237819; E.P. 27773/09). Kalle and Co. (E.P. 233452) have claimed the production of certain vat dyes by alkali fusion of acenaphthenone derivatives of general formula,

where R is a substituted or unsubstituted aryl group.

With the exception of these recent attempts to prepare vat dyes, very little or rather no systematic work has been done upon acenaphthenone derivatives. In the two previous communications in this series (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 103, 297) pyrilium, indole and acridine derivatives from acenaphthenone have been described. In the preparation of all the above three types of compounds both the CO and the CH₂ groups of acenaphthenone were utilised. The present paper deals with the reactivity of acenaphthenone through its CH₂ group alone.

Action of Nitroso Compounds on Acenaphthenone.

Aromatic nitroso compounds very readily react with reactive methylene groups (*cf.* Ehrlich and Sachs, *Ber.*, 1899, 32, 2341; Sachs, *Ber.*, 1900, 33, 959; Sachs and Bry, *Ber.*, 1901 34, 118, etc.). Recently Pandse and Dutt (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 8, 953) have shown that aromatic nitroso and isonitroso compounds in presence of glacial acetic acid or acetic anhydride condense with thiohydantoin forming products many of which are fairly

deep coloured and well adapted for dyeing on wool and silk. It was therefore expected that similar dyes could also be prepared by the condensation of acenaphthenone with various aromatic nitroso compounds.

In attempting to effect the condensation in presence of acetic anhydride, there was obtained every time only a dark resinous product from which nothing definite could be isolated. Glacial acetic acid and fused sodium acetate, 10% alcoholic potash, diethylamine, and piperidine were next tried as condensing agents and the following nitroso compounds were used: nitrosophenol, nitrosodimethylaniline and nitrosothymol. When the condensations were attempted at temperatures ranging between 60-80° using acetic acid and sodium acetate one and the same product, bisacenaphthylidenediketone (M), was obtained with every nitroso compound.

This compound had already been obtained by Graebe and Gfeller (*Annalen*, 1898, 276, 17) and afterwards been synthesised by the condensation of acenaphthenone with acenaphthenequinone (D.R.P. 212858). It has also been prepared in the course of the present investigation by condensing acenaphthenone with acenaphthenequinone and its identity established by mixed melting point determination and study of other properties. The formation of such a compound (*viz.*, bisacenaphthylidenediketone) can be explained only if a part of acenaphthenone is oxidised by the nitroso compounds to acenaphthenequinone which in turn condenses with the unchanged acenaphthenone.

Acenaphthenone has also been condensed with phenanthraquinone but here only the aldol phase could be isolated. When condensation was tried with benzil the normal product was only obtained, the aldol phase being lost sight of.

Condensation of Aromatic Aldehydes with Acenaphthenone.

Graebe and Jequer (*Annalen*, 1896, **290**, 204) prepared benzyldeneacenaphthenone by the condensation of acenaphthenone with benzaldehyde. The work of Graebe and Jequer (*loc. cit.*) has now been extended and the following aldehydes were condensed with acenaphthenone:

(1) Anisic aldehyde, (2) salicylic aldehyde,* (3) *m*-hydroxybenzaldehyde, (4) *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde, (5) *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde, (6) *p*-acetylaminobenzaldehyde, (7) cinnamic aldehyde.

Action of amyl nitrite on acenaphthenone.—The reactivity of the CH_2 group towards amyl nitrite and hydrochloric acid has also been studied. By following the method adopted for the preparation of isonitrosoflavanone from flavanone (Kostanecki and Szabranski (*Ber.*, 1904, **37**, 2819), isonitroso derivative of acenaphthenone has been prepared. This is, as expected by theory, found to be identical with the monoxime of acenaphthenequinone.

* Kalle & Co. (E. P. 233452) claims the preparation of vat dyes by the potash fusion of certain acenaphthenone-aldehyde condensation products. But even in the original patent literature with the exception of the name of salicylic aldehyde derivative no mention is made about the compounds prepared or utilised.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Action of Nitroso Compounds on Acenaphthenone.

(a) *With p-nitrosodimethylaniline.*—To a mixture of acenaphthenone (0.5 g.) and freshly prepared *p*-nitrosodimethylaniline (0.43 g.) dissolved in 10 c.c. of acetic acid, 2-3 g. of fused sodium acetate were added. The mixture was heated on the water-bath for about 1½-2 hours when some orange needles began to separate. The heating was continued for another ½ hour to complete the separation of the crystals. These were filtered hot and recrystallised in beautiful orange needles from a large quantity of acetic acid in which they are only sparingly soluble, m. p. 287-88°. It does not contain nitrogen and was identified to be bisacenaphthylidenediketone (*vide infra*).

(b) *With nitrosophenol.*—Acenaphthenone (0.5 g.) and freshly prepared nitrosophenol (0.38 g.) were dissolved in 10 c.c. of acetic acid and 2-3 g. of fused sodium acetate added and the mixture refluxed on the water-bath for 3-4 hours. As in the preceding experiment, orange-yellow needles separated which after recrystallisation were identified to be bisacenaphthylidenediketone (*vide infra*).

(c) *With nitrosothymol.*—Acenaphthenone (0.5 g.) and nitrosothymol (0.52 g.) were dissolved in acetic acid to which 2-3 g. of sodium acetate had been previously added and proceeded as in the two preceding cases. The separated crystals were again found to be identical with bisacenaphthylidenediketone.

As the nitroso compounds acted as oxidising agents in the hot state, attempts were next made to bring about the desired condensation in the cold, but no change was observed even on standing for 3-4 days.

Then the condensation was tried in presence of condensing agents like alcoholic caustic potash, piperidine or diethylamine.

(d) *Action of nitrosophenol on acenaphthenone in presence of caustic potash.*—Acenaphthenone (0.5 g.) and nitrosophenol (0.38 g.) were dissolved in the smallest quantity of alcohol, a few drops of 10% alcoholic potash added and the mixture allowed to stand for 10-12 hours. The separated crystalline precipitate on examination was found to be a mixture of orange-yellow needles and white prismatic plates. The crystals were filtered and extracted with boiling acetic acid when the major portion of the orange-yellow substance together with very little of the white substance went into solution. The pre-

precipitate left after extraction with acetic acid was dissolved in chloroform and either ether or petroleum ether added to the chloroform solution when only the white prismatic plates separated.

This was filtered, m.p. 289-90°. The substance does not contain nitrogen. It is soluble in pyridine, almost insoluble in alcohol. It gives a straw-yellow colour with concentrated sulphuric acid and develops a greenish fluorescence after keeping for some time. (Found: C, 85.57; H, 4.42. $C_{12}H_8O$ requires C, 85.72; H, 4.76 per cent.).

The acetic acid extract was diluted with water and the separated precipitate after repeated crystallisations from acetic acid was identified to be bisacenaphthylidenediketone.

Condensations with *p*-nitrosodimethylaniline and nitrosothymol were next tried using alcoholic potash as the condensing agent, but the results were identical with that of the preceding experiment, only with this difference that the relative yields of the two products, *viz.*, (1) bisacenaphthylidenediketone and (2) the white prismatic plates were somewhat different.

The experiments were also repeated by using diethylamine and piperidine respectively, as condensing agents, but with no better results and only the same two products could be isolated.

That the orange-yellow needles obtained in each attempt to condense acenaphthenone with nitroso compounds were identical with bisacenaphthylidenediketone (*vide infra*), was established in each case by mixed melting point determinations.

Condensation of Acenaphthenone with o-Diketones.

Bisacenaphthylidenediketone was easily obtained as orange-yellow needles by heating on the water-bath a solution of acenaphthenone (0.5 g.) and acenaphthenequinone (0.54 g.) in 10 c.c. of acetic acid with fused sodium acetate (2-3 g.) for 3-4 hours. After recrystallisation from acetic acid it melted at 287-88° (Graebe and Jequier give the m.p. 295°). (Found: C, 86.82. H, 3.85. $C_{24}H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 86.76; H, 3.61 per cent.).

Aldol condensation of acenaphthenone and acenaphthenequinone.—The original filtrate from the preceding experiment was diluted with water, when a sticky solid separated. This was filtered and a portion of it was found to be highly soluble in alcohol, benzene, acetic acid or pyridine. The solid was extracted with cold alcohol and filtered from the insoluble residue. The filtrate was boiled with animal

charcoal and filtered. The filtrate on dilution yielded a microcrystalline powder which was then extracted with cold pyridine and filtered. To the hot pyridine solution hot water was slowly added when slightly pinkish plates separated on cooling. The crystals were filtered, washed repeatedly with dilute hydrochloric acid and then dried in a steam oven to free it from any pyridine left adhering, m.p. 168-69°. The yield of this product was very poor. The substance is slightly soluble in caustic potash solution with a blue fluorescence. In alcoholic potash it gives a green-coloured solution. It is highly soluble in alcohol, benzene, chloroform, etc. (Found: C, 82.73; H, 3.86. $C_{24}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 82.28; H, 4.0 per cent.).

A better yield of the above aldol product (50 % after purification) was obtained by the condensation of acenaphthenone with acenaphthenequinone at a lower temperature (60-70°) and heating it for somewhat longer time (5-6 hours). Under these conditions the formation of bisacenaphthylidenediketone was entirely avoided.

The aldol product easily parted with water when heated for about $\frac{1}{2}$ - $\frac{3}{4}$ hour with excess of acetic anhydride and sodium acetate and yielded bisacenaphthylidenediketone, identified by mixed melting point determination.

Condensation of Acenaphthenone with Phenanthraquinone.

Acenaphthenone (0.5 g.) and phenanthraquinone (0.62 g.) were dissolved in glacial acetic acid (15 c.c.) and sodium acetate (2.3 g.) added and was heated on the water-bath for 6-8 hours. No precipitate appeared during heating. After cooling the reaction mixture was diluted with water and the precipitate filtered. The solubility of the product thus formed was only very slightly different from that of phenanthraquinone whereas that of acenaphthenone was very different. By washing the precipitate with rectified spirit it was freed from acenaphthenone. The condensation product is less soluble in acetic acid than phenanthraquinone. Thus by repeatedly

dissolving the precipitate in acetic acid and then adding water in such a proportion as not to precipitate the whole thing, a product was obtained which however could not be crystallised from any solvent. It is fairly soluble in alcohol, highly so in benzene or chloroform. This product, purified from acetic acid by fractional precipitation by water, was obtained as a microcrystalline powder, decomposing at 185-87°, without melting. The yield, however, of the purified product was extremely poor. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with a greenish-yellow colour. (Found: C, 82.26; H, 4.64. $C_{26}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 82.96; H, 4.25 per cent.).

Condensation of Acenaphthenone with Benzil.

Acenaphthenone (0.5 g.) and benzil (0.68 g.) were dissolved in the smallest quantity of alcohol and a few drops of 10% alcoholic potash (10%) added, when immediately a beautiful crystalline precipitate separated. The filtered precipitate was washed with 50% alcohol and was purified by recrystallisation from dilute alcohol as glistening hexagonal yellow plates, m. p. 205°. It is sparingly soluble in absolute alcohol or acetic acid and highly soluble in benzene or chloroform. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with a scarlet red colour and is reprecipitated on dilution. (Found: C, 86.32; H, 4.42. $O_{26}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 86.68; H, 4.4 per cent.).

Condensation of Aromatic Aldehydes with Acenaphthenone.

Anisylideneacenaphthenone.

Equimolecular quantities of acenaphthenone and anisic aldehyde were dissolved in the smallest quantity of alcohol and a few drops

of 10% alcoholic potash added. After some time a resinous product separated. This was filtered, washed with 40% alcohol, and then was dissolved in boiling alcohol, decolorised by animal charcoal and filtered hot. The filtrate, on dilution with a few drops of water, deposited on cooling beautiful yellow parallelepiped crystals, *m. p.* 126.5-27°. It is sparingly soluble in acetic acid or ether, highly soluble in chloroform or benzene. It gives a scarlet red solution with concentrated sulphuric acid and is reprecipitated on dilution. (Found: C, 83.51; H, 5.0. $C_{20}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 83.90; H, 4.89 per cent.).

The following benzylideneacenaphthenones were prepared in a similar way (except where otherwise mentioned) as the preceding compound. They generally separated as solids without any difficulty.

m-Nitrobenzylideneacenaphthenone from acenaphthenone and *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde separated from dilute alcohol in straw coloured rectangular plates, mixed up with some microcrystalline mass, *m. p.* 177-78°. It is highly soluble in benzene or chloroform and sparingly soluble in ether. It gives a blood-red solution with concentrated sulphuric acid and on dilution the original substance is reprecipitated. (Found: N, 4.87. $C_{19}H_{11}O_3N$ requires N, 4.65 per cent.).

p-Nitrobenzylideneacenaphthenone from acenaphthenone and *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde, forms yellow silky needles from acetic acid, *m. p.* 239-40°. It is soluble in alcohol, acetic acid, and highly so in chloroform or benzene and is insoluble in ether. It gives deep red colour with concentrated sulphuric acid. (Found: N, 4.93. $C_{19}H_{11}O_3N$ requires N, 4.65 per cent.).

Cinnamylideneacenaphthenone from cinnamic aldehyde and acenaphthenone, separated as a microcrystalline powder on the addition of water to the alcoholic solution of the reaction mixture after 24 hours of standing. It was purified by repeatedly dissolving in alcohol and reprecipitating by the addition of water containing a few drops of hydrochloric acid, *m. p.* 214-15° with previous shrinking at 196°. It is soluble in benzene, chloroform or acetic acid. It gives an yellowish brown solution with concentrated sulphuric acid and is reprecipitated on dilution. (Found: C, 89.17; H, 5.1. $C_{21}H_{14}O$ requires C, 89.87; H, 4.96 per cent.).

Salicylideneacenaphthenone from salicylic aldehyde and acenaphthenone, has already been described under pyrylium compounds.

(*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 105), m. p. 186-87°. (Found: C, 83.79; H, 4.53. $C_{19}H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 83.81; H, 4.41 per cent.).

m-Hydroxybenzylideneacenaphthenone was prepared from *m*-hydroxybenzaldehyde and acenaphthenone in the same way as the preceding compounds and crystallised from dilute alcohol as pale yellow rectangular plates, m. p. 191-92°. It dissolves in alkali and in concentrated sulphuric acid with a reddish yellow colour. (Found: C, 83.51; H, 4.59. $C_{19}H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 83.81; H, 4.41 per cent.).

p-Acetylaminobenzylideneacenaphthenone, from acenaphthenone and *p*-acetylaminobenzaldehyde, crystallised from hot boiling alcohol in long yellow needles, m. p. 255.5-56°. It is soluble in chloroform or benzene. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with a reddish orange colour and is reprecipitated on dilution. (Found: N, 4.67. $C_{21}H_{15}O_2N$ requires N, 4.47 per cent.).

Preparation of isonitrosoacenaphthenone.—A mixture of acenaphthenone (1 g.) and amyl nitrite (1.03 g.) in alcohol (20 c.c.) was heated on the water-bath in a round-bottomed flask under a reflux. When the solution was just boiling hydrochloric acid (4.12 g., *d* 1.19) was added drop by drop. The colour of the solution changed from yellow to orange-red. Addition of hydrochloric acid was completed in about $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. On cooling a solid separated. To the cold mixture water was added and the precipitate filtered. This was extracted with dilute sodium hydroxide solution, when a part went into solution forming a reddish solution. The solution was then filtered and to the filtrate dilute acetic acid was added which gave a precipitate. This was crystallised from dilute alcohol in fine ash-coloured needles. The isonitroso compound thus prepared was found, as expected by theory, to be identical with the monoxime of acenaphthenequinone. This was confirmed by a mixed melting point determination.